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An X-Ray of Security Practices in Nigerian University Libraries

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

A recent study showed no significant relationship between the security measures adopted and the rate of crime - theft and mutilation of information resources- in Abia State University Library, Uturu (ABSU); Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Library, Umudike (MOUUAU); Evan Enwerem University Library, Owerri (EEU); and Federal University of Technology Library, Owerri (FUTO). Consequently, in an attempt to avoid a situation where new or existing libraries would move to employ or depend on the security measures investigated and found unsuitable to check theft and mutilation crimes in the afore mentioned Nigerian university libraries, the researchers moved to publish the security practices employed in these university libraries. The survey research method was used to collate data, which were analysed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Security practices with mean scores of 2.5 and above were accepted. The researchers found a total of fourteen (14), nineteen (19), nineteen (19) and twenty-two (22) security practises employed in ABSU, EEU, MOUUAU and FUTO libraries respectively.

Keywords: Security, Libraries, University, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Security refers to a process designed to protect something or somebody against danger. It is an act of preventing crime, where in the case of library resources, it prevents un-authorized removal or loss of materials, usually as a result of intruders' or thieves' interference (Ajegbomogun, 2004). Conceptually, it means the overall manner in which policies, programmes, procedures, or measures are deployed to mitigate risk and ensure access to a particular resource feared to disappear. Relatively, a security practice simply refers to the different types of actions, measures or practices adopted to stop a crime.

Libraries in Nigeria are performing a great chunk of their activities traditionally. A recent study has shown that crime against library collections, otherwise known as information resources, is on the increase in a number of Nigerian university libraries. It was observed that there was no significant relationship found between the security measures adopted and the rate of crime - theft and mutilation of information resources - in some Nigerian university libraries (Uzuegbu, 2011). In avoidance of a situation where new or existing libraries would move to employ or depend on the security measures investigated and found unsuitable to check theft and mutilation crimes in university libraries, this paper is poised at publishing the security practices employed in some Nigerian university libraries. The Nigerian university libraries under study are: Abia State University Library, Uturu (ABSU); Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Library, Umudike (MOUUAU); Evan Enwerem University Library, Owerri (EEU); and Federal University of Technology Library, Owerri (FUTO).

Literature Review

Library services can only be achieved through the availability of library collections. Nkiki and Yusuf (2008) observe that information is an essential part of a nation's wealth and access to it is a basic human right. A university library houses a wide variety of information resources. Information is not only a national resource but also a medium for social communication. Thanuskodi (2009) observes that the rate of declining budgets and a higher subscription cost facing academic institutions is making it seemingly impossible for libraries to meet the rising information needs of

university students, let alone allowing the available collections lost. As a matter of fact, criminal activities against information resources are a formidable obstacle to information access and use - not only posing a serious problem that needs urgent attention, but also constituting a big cost to scholarship (Ugah, 2007; Ratcliff, 1992). Chaney and MacDougall (1994) reason that university library collections are at risk to one form of abuse or the other. Their contents and value, even their worth financially, which may not be attainable for many classes of the user public, among other things can lead to their being eyed wrongful. The effect of this anomaly can be traced back to the pains taken by the ancient Babylonian scribes to recopy lost library items. The effect then is still equal to a loss of a contemporary university library material, irrespective of whatever we think modernity has given humanity in terms of multiple printing. Thompson (1977) realized how great a loss of material could be to an archives house and records that, even though the rate of crime then was relatively low, there were varied punishments for withholding over-due library books or damaging them, let alone stealing them. Thus the surging rate of theft, mutilation, and all manner of crimes against library collections is almost in tandem with the volume of availability of the materials, not failing at all to result in greater scarcity and deprivation of free knowledge, save for the availability of computer aided information access, which Anunobi and Okoye (2008) also agree not to be safe as well.

Consequently, different libraries have adopted varying security measures for their collections' safety. McComb (2004) writes that physical (non-electronic) security, electronic security and security policies/procedures are substantial methods for securing information resources of all kinds of libraries. Physical security includes architectural considerations, the use of personnel, and security hardware to prevent crimes against library collections. Electronic security system refers to the use of equipment which typically provide alarm notification to the appropriate authority on entry control and site surveillance. Major elements of the electronic security system include burglary protection, collection security (hidden on materials), access control (systems that directly "read" unique personal characteristics such as voice quality, hand geometry, identity cards, etc.), and video surveillance, particularly the CCTV system. Sensors (detectors) to detect an intrusion and alarms (to notify appropriate authorities) are the facilities that make this type of security electronic (www.alarm.org). On the other hand, security policies and procedures include all created and implemented security policies, procedures, and plans for the library. These should, at least, include entry and exit procedures, room registration procedures, personal belonging restrictions, special collections use policies, and entry key management procedures (McComb, 2004).

In another perspective, Nwalo (2003) argues that library crime may not be prevented or checked to its minimal state as long as the security personnel are not directly under the library department. He states that the security men are loyal to the security department rather than to the library authority. This situation makes it difficult for the librarians to control security matters in their library as their orders may be flouted. He concludes by arguing that aside from the divided loyalty experiences which result in poor security in the library, the security personnel, mostly the ones in Nigerian university libraries, are not literate enough to understand the full import of their duties. In support, Hinks (1992) and Macdonald (1992) posit that staff training is very important, especially providing grounds where the staff will have the opportunity to discuss both the acceptable behaviours as well as the tolerance level of every staff in any aggrieved situation. They agree also that not only does the training expose staff to the nature of the problem and how to handle them, it can also avail them many other things like acquainting them with the modern trend of security gadgets and how they can be operated or worked with. However, Oder (2004) strongly maintains that security measures such as supervision, patrolling, and surveillance are lacking in libraries while keys to various collection halls are kept unsecured, if not in plain sight of the users. Although Brown (2007) suggests coordinated policies as a means of addressing general library threats, there seems to be a greater need for constant security measures which a good and comprehensive library user education can surmount to a great extent.

Meanwhile, Olorunsola (1987) reveals that the growth of universities in all perspectives relates to the rate of crime experienced. It is worthy of note that not all crimes in academic libraries are committed by patrons. Most crimes, he says, are done by the staff. Lorenzen (1996) agrees with this, arguing that since library employees know how to defeat the security system, they can equally accomplish crimes that would be difficult to prevent. Meanwhile, Ives (1996) believes that library staff and patrons remain the greatest potential threats to university collection security. It is also noted by Bello (1998) that whenever users' demand on a library material is far more than the supply and availability of such materials, criminal acts proceed. This result in competition for resources, which invariably tempts users to steal, mutilate, or engage in illegal borrowing. Some library criminal acts that appear to be universal include: mutilation, theft, disruptive behaviours, disaster, and poor personnel security. Lorenzen (1996) says that what most times causes mutilation is that most students do not consider the needs of other students nor are they familiar with the roles of the library as to know they are committing crime by engaging in those acts. In a separate view, Momodu (2002) and Ajegbomogun (2004) maintain that library crimes also include varying degrees of delinquency, while Thomas (2000) and Oder (2004) agree that security personnel inefficiency is also a big avenue to library crime, especially in academic libraries. Hence, as the price of library materials continue to escalate, and library budgets do not usually keep pace with inflation, the importance of securing our collections takes on ever-increasing importance (Johansson, 1996).

Relevantly, Olorunsola (1987), Bello (1998), Nwogu and Anunobi (2002), Ugah (2002) and Adewuyi and Adekanye (2011) agree that security measures in Nigerian university libraries vis-à-vis theft and mutilation crimes are:

- Building of library with concrete
- Protecting windows with wire gauze
- The use of porter at entrance and exit doors of the library
- Employing security personnel
- Unstable electronic detector machine (for University of Lagos Library).
- Irregular monitoring and patrol in the readers service hall
- Unwritten policies as regards punishments for offenders
- Warning students during freshmen orientation talk
- Using post bills to warn students
- Staff personal advice or appeal to students.

Other researches have shown that the use of personnel, electronic devices, building, facilities, verbal communication/written communication (policies), mutual relationship (staff/patron agreement), amongst others are security practises that can curtail varying kinds of crime done to library collections (Van Gage-Babcock, 1963; Nwamefor, 1974; Nicewamer and Heaton, 1995; Abifarin, 1997; Susanna & Matheson, 2000; Ajegbomogun, 2004; Ajala and Oyeboade, 2008; Nort, 2010; Martell, 2010; Maidabino, 2010).

In sum, the literature review points at personnel, infrastructure, physical facilities, electronic devices and security policies as acclaimed methods of preventing crimes against library collections. Of course, the reason why security must be enforced in university libraries is not limited to the increasing growth rate of university community members but also relates to the surging price of library materials daily. This is why Nigerian university libraries adopt varying security measures to safeguard their library collections. Nevertheless, it is observed that there is no literature, as at the time of this study, which provides detailed information on the varying security practices employed in Nigerian university libraries. Against this backdrop, it is hoped that this study shall contribute to fill the gap by showing the security practices in ABSU, EEU, MOUAU and FUTO libraries.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was adopted for the study. Uzuegbu's (2011) work - a Master's degree dissertation completed and scored in November 2011 - was surveyed and the unarranged security practises employed in the four university libraries studied were extracted. The libraries are ABSU, EEU, MOUAU and FUTO. However, for the sake of the gap in time of dissertation submission and date of this paper (August, 2012), the researchers went a step further to increase the value of the data in the dissertation work by visiting the studied libraries to re-field the questionnaire instrument and interview some of the staff of the libraries. The population of the study consists of all the one hundred and sixty-eight (168) library staff members of the four libraries. This figure does not include the secretarial staff members in these libraries. The entire population was used because they are accessible. The table below summarizes the distribution of the population according to their institutions.

Table.1: **Distribution of the Study Population According to the Institutions.**

University Libraries	Staff Size
ABSU	21
EEU	19
MOUAU	39
FUTO	89
Total	168

Source: i) Staff of the libraries of ABSU and MOUAU.

ii) Students' handbook of EEU, and Library bulletin and accession list of FUTO.

A four-point-scale or modified Likert questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was fielded to all staff of the libraries. Each questionnaire comprised of thirty-seven (37) questions intended to extract information on the type of security practices adopted by the libraries under study. Respondents were requested to

tick on one of the following: SA = strongly agree, A = agree, D = disagree, SD = strongly disagree, which the researcher weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. Data collected from the questionnaire were presented and analyzed using mean scores and frequency tables on the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 16.0). The percentage formula used is:

$$\frac{N \times 100}{P}$$

Where N = number of respondents, P = total population of study.

The mean was calculated as: $\frac{4 + 3 + 2 + 1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$ (at one decimal place)

The decision was that any item with a mean of 2.5 and above will be accepted as 'Agreed' (A) while, any item with a mean below 2.5 was considered Disagreed (D).

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data are analyzed together for all institutions with the SPSS 16.0 package (See Appendix). Out of one hundred and sixty eight (168) copies of the questionnaire distributed, one hundred and eight (108) were valid for data analysis. The collected instrument is 64% of the total instrument and as such is used for data presentation and analysis. The distribution of data instrument collection is shown in table 2 below:

Table 2: Distribution and Return Rate of Questionnaire Instrument

University Libraries	Number of Copies Distributed	Number Returned and Valid for Analysis	%
ABSU	21	17	80.9
EEU	19	15	78.9
MOUAU	39	30	76.9
FUTO	89	46	51.6
Total	168	108	64

The researchers proceeded to find out the security practices, with their level of acceptance, adopted by each of the libraries in their attempt to tackle crime against information resources. In ABSU library, the security practices adopted are clearly presented in table 3 below in order of the degree of acceptance.

Table 3: Security Practices in ABSU Library

S/N	Security Practices	Acceptance Level (Mean)
1	The library has a secured place, guided by a porter, where all users of the library keep their bags and boxes before entering the library	3.6
2	The library employs one entrance door and one exit route for its users	3.6
3	The windows of the library are fortified with strong wire gauze	3.6
4	The library staff check users ID cards and record their data before they are allowed to use the library	3.5
5	The library has a written statement against library crime and corresponding punishments	3.3
6	The library has photocopy services very close to the reader services units (main circulation, reference and serials units)	3.3
7	The library ensures that all users are searched thoroughly at the library exit	3.1

Table 3 continues

8	The library uses bill boards, leaflet, orientations, etc. to remind library users of the punishments for stealing or destroying a library material	3.1
9	The library always bans anybody caught in stealing or destroying library materials from using the library for a period of time	2.9
10	In the library, the porters are supervised by a librarian or library officer	2.8
11	The library sensitizes users on dangers of stealing or destroying materials of the library	2.7
12	The library usually asks the university management to expel or suspend students caught stealing or destroying library materials	2.5
13	The library punishes any staff that colludes with library criminals	2.5
14	Staff examines each reading material users consulted	2.5

Evident on table 3 above, fourteen (14) security measures are practiced in ABSU library.

Table 4: Security Practices in EEU Library

S/N	Security Practices	Acceptance Level (Mean)
1	There is a photocopy service very close to the reader services units (main circulation, reference and serials units)	3.5
2	The university security unit posts their staff to the library for every day supervision	3.3
3	Staff ensures that all users are searched thoroughly at the library exit	3.3
4	Staff walk round the reading hall continuously to monitor readers and ensure that there are no foul practices going on at various reading carrels	3.3
5	There is only one entrance door and one exit route for its users	3.3
6	The windows are fortified with strong wire gauze	3.3
7	Staff examine each reading material users consulted	3.2
8	The porters in the library are on ground from opening of library to its closing of each day's service	3.2
9	There is a secured place, guided by a porter, where all users of the library keep their bags and boxes before entering the library	3.2
10	Users are sensitized on the dangers of stealing or destroying materials of the library	3.1
11	The entrance and exit routes are fortified with iron that may not be easily broken forcefully at night	3.0
12	There is a-24hr security patrol in the library block	2.9
13	The university security personnel that are posted to the library are able-bodied men	2.7
14	Staff check users ID cards and record their data before they are allowed to use the library	2.7
15	There are at least two porters or security personnel in every reader services unit of the library	2.6
16	The porters are supervised by a librarian or library officer	2.6
17	Punishments are given to any staff that colludes with library criminals	2.5
18	Users are in most cases, the people that report the stealing or destroying acts of their fellow users to our staff	2.5
19	There is restriction of access to most collections	2.5

In EEU library, the table above shows that a total of nineteen (19) security methods are adopted to check crimes against library collections.

Table 5: Security Practices in MOUAU Library

S/N	Security Practices	Acceptance Level (Mean)
1	There is a CCTV cable mounted in the main library and monitored in University Librarian's office	3.6
2	Staff ensure that all users are searched thoroughly at the library exit	3.4
3	The university security unit posts their staff to the library for every day supervision	3.4
4	There is only one entrance door and one exit route for its users	3.3
5	The windows are fortified with strong wire gauze	3.2
6	There is a secured place, guided by a porter, where all users of the library keep their bags and boxes before entering the library	3.2
7	Punishments are given to any staff that colludes with library criminals	3.1
8	The porters in the library are on ground from opening of library to its closing of each day's service	3.1
9	Staff examine each reading material users consulted	3.0
10	The librarian usually asks the university management to expel or suspend students caught stealing or destroying library materials	3.0
11	Users caught stealing or destroying library materials are barred from using the library for a period of time	2.9
12	There is a-24hr security patrol in the library block	2.9
13	There are at least two porters or security personnel in every reader services unit of the library	2.8
14	The identity of patrons who commit theft and mutilation are exposed to the university community	2.8
15	Users are sensitized to the dangers of stealing or destroying materials of the library	2.8
16	The porters are supervised by a librarian or library officer	2.7
17	Staff check users ID cards and record their data before they are allowed to use the library	2.7
18	There is a written statement or policy against library crime and corresponding punishments	2.6
19	There is restriction of access to most collections	2.6

In MOUAU library, a total of nineteen (19) security measures are enforced to safeguard the collections of the library. This is less than the number shown in Uzuegbu's (2011) work (18 security practices). It is observed that CCTV Cable is the new practice here, which is not contained in his research. A respondent told the researchers that the CCTV cable was installed recently.

Table 6: Security Practices in FUTO Library

S/N	Security Practices	Acceptance Level (Mean)
1	The porters in the library are on ground from opening of library to its closing of each day's service	3.6
2	There is a photocopy service very close to the reader services units (main circulation, reference and serials units)	3.6
3	There are at least two porters or security personnel in every reader services unit of the library	3.5
4	Staff ensure that all users are searched thoroughly at the library exit	3.5
5	There is only one entrance door and one exit route for its users	3.4
6	There is a secured place, guided by a porter, where all users of the library keep their bags and boxes before entering the library	3.3
7	The windows are fortified with strong wire gauze	3.3
8	Users are sensitized to the dangers of stealing or destroying materials of the library	3.2
9	There is a written statement or policy against library crime and corresponding punishments	3.2
10	The university security personnel that are posted to the library are able-bodied men	3.1
11	Staff that collude with library criminals are punished	3.1
12	The porters are supervised by a librarian or library officer	3.1
13	Staff walk round the reading hall continuously to monitor readers and ensure that there are no foul practices going on in various reading carrels	3.0
14	Users caught stealing or destroying library materials are barred from using the library for a period of time	3.0
15	The entrance and exit routes are very fortified with iron that may not be easily broken forcefully at night	3.0
16	The university security unit posts their staff to the library for every day supervision	2.8
17	Bill boards, leaflet, orientations, etc. are used to remind library users of the punishments for stealing or destroying a library material	2.8
18	There is restriction of access to most collections	2.7
19	Staff examine each reading material users consulted	2.6
20	The readers always hold a minimum of ten copies of every reading material that is daily sought by users	2.6
21	Staff check users' ID cards and record their data before they are allowed to use the library	2.6
22	There is a 24hr security patrol in the library block	2.5

Meanwhile, in FUTO library, twenty-two (22) security measures are adopted to safeguard the information resources of the library.

So far, it is clear that out of an exhaustive list of thirty-seven various (37) security practices fielded to respondents of each library to indicate the ones practised in their libraries, only fourteen (14) are adopted in ABSU library, nineteen (19) practised in EEU library, nineteen (19) in MOUAW library and twenty-two (22) in FUTO library. It is also observed that within the period of 5 months (assumed gap in Uzuegbu's (2011) dissertation and period of this research) security practises have remained the same except in MOUAW library where the use of CCTV cable was introduced.

Note that while some good security measures like the use of electronic devices such as CCTV (for EEU, ABSU and FUTO libraries), alarm door system, turnstile systems, amongst others are not practised in the libraries. Although none of the libraries engage men and women above forty (40) years as porters, there has not been

corresponding increase in porters for adequate policing as the population of each of the university is growing, neither are there trainings for the available porters. Other security practises generally not adopted by the libraries include users signing in and out on each visit, establishment of users club, making staff submit their bag for search before going for the day, and keeping detailed records of all criminal activities and incidents in the libraries, amongst others.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

This study has successfully shown the various security practices in ABSU, EEU, MOUAU and FUTO libraries. It is observed that the security practises implemented in libraries vary in number. Already, Uzuegbu (2011) has shown that there is no relationship between the security practises and theft and mutilation of the library collections. But, no one is sure as to say that: the higher the security practises the lower the rate of crimes against library collection. Thus, the researchers suggest that a study can be conducted to find if the number of security practises enforced in a library influences the extent of criminal occurrences and incidence in the library.

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